
From Shreni to Swiggy: A Comparative Analysis of Contemporary Gig Economy with Ancient Indian Informal Labor Systems

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Abstract The contemporary Gig Economy driven by digital platforms and algorithmic management is often portrayed as a nuanced development in labor markets. However, this study argues that task-based, flexible, and informal work structures have been present in India's labor markets since time immemorial. The present study demonstrates a comparative analysis of the Informal labor systems outlined in ancient Indian texts most notably in Kautilya's Arthshastra with the contemporary platform-mediated Gig work. Using a mixed-methods design, the research investigates the continuities and transformations in employment arrangements, worker autonomy, and regulatory frameworks. The study is based on the qualitative historical analysis of texts such as the Arthshastra, alongside secondary literature on labor guilds (Shreni), the jajmani system, and pre-modern occupational mobility which is further followed by survey of Gig workers through structured surveys and in-depth interviews. The comparative analysis reveals a few striking parallels: Both systems exhibit contract-based, non-permanent work tied to individual skills; limited job security; and dependence on intermediaries. However, critical differences also emerge, especially regarding worker autonomy, regulation, and technological control. While ancient models often included the role of the state and community wellbeing, today's gig work is shaped by precarious work and algorithmic governance with limited protection. The study concludes that India's gig economy is not an entirely new phenomenon, but a digital reincarnation of older labor forms, repackaged within neoliberal and tech-mediated structures and recognizing this continuity can help address the vulnerabilities of modern Gig workers.

Keywords: Platform workers, Arthshastra, History, Gig Economy

1. Introduction

In India, platform-based work such as food delivery, ride-hailing, and digital freelancing has grown rapidly, particularly after the COVID-19 pandemic reshaped labor demand (Mehrotra & Parida, 2022). The platform economy, a subset of Gig Economy is often characterized by short-term, task-based, and technology-mediated labour exchanges. This phenomenon is generally perceived as a distinctly modern phenomenon (De Stefano, 2016; Kalleberg & Dunn, 2016). However, the phenomenon of temporary, task-oriented labor is not entirely new to the Indian context and its conceptual roots can be traced back to ancient Indian origin. Historical evidence

demonstrates that task-based, contractual, and flexible forms of labor have existed in India since time immemorial. In the light of this, ancient Indian texts particularly the Arthshastra, authored by Kautilya in the 4th century BCE provides detailed accounts of labour arrangements, contractual obligations, and state regulation of service providers (Rangarajan, 1992).

India's pre-modern economy was characterized by guild-like institutions (Shreni) that coordinated artisanal and mercantile labor. Shreni acted as intermediaries, regulating entry into trades, setting quality standards, and mediating between rulers and workers (Ray, 2004). In many ways, these resembled proto-platforms—organizing dispersed workers, matching them with demand, and ensuring accountability. Likewise, itinerant laborers, mercenaries, and seasonal agricultural workers took on temporary, project-specific roles—closely paralleling the short-term “gigs” of today. Colonial rule further entrenched informal labor by dismantling traditional guilds and redirecting India's economic base toward extractive industries (Bayly, 2012). The erosion of formalized community-based labor protections forced workers into casual, insecure roles that bear striking resemblance to today's platformized precarity. Post-independence, state-led industrialization promised stable employment through public sector enterprises, but the liberalization of the 1990s reversed this trend. The rise of digital platforms since the 2010s has reconfigured informal work into technologically mediated forms—what many call the “new gig economy” (Mehrotra & Parida, 2021).

This historical parallel raises two critical questions: Shall the modern day gig economy be understood as a modern manifestation of older contractual labor systems in India? What continuities and divergences are expected to exist between ancient models of work and contemporary platform-based arrangements? Addressing these questions is significant for developing a nuanced perspective on the evolution of labor forms, labor rights and labor policy regulation.

The present study conducts a comparative mixed-methods analysis, combining survey data and interviews with gig workers in Gujarat, alongside a textual examination of ancient economic texts particularly the Arthshastra. The objective is not only to trace the historical lineage of task-based work but also to highlight policy lessons that may inform the regulation of digital labor markets in India today.

2. Literature Review

Ancient Contexts: Arthshastra and Shreni

The Arthshastra, attributed to Kautilya (Chanakya), presents one of the earliest systematic works on political economy and governance in India. It describes multiple occupational categories—including artisans, builders, entertainers, and mercenaries—whose livelihoods depended on short-term contractual engagements (Kangle, 1965; Rangarajan, 1992). For instance, dancers, musicians, and courtesans were often hired for single events, reflecting clear parallels with contemporary gig work in cultural and creative industries. Moreover, the text specifies wage structures and contractual obligations, underscoring the institutional recognition of non-permanent work.

Shrenis (guilds), which flourished in the Mauryan and Gupta periods, can be viewed as early collectives organizing gig-like workers. Shrenis not only facilitated trade and labour contracts but also served welfare functions, providing protection for members and negotiating with the state (Ray, 2004). Their decline under colonialism disrupted these protective structures, foreshadowing the precariousness seen in the modern gig economy. These Shrenis shall be seen as parallel to platforms functioning in the present day Gig Economy.

Medieval and Colonial Periods

In medieval India, religious performers, craftsmen and agricultural labourers continued to operate outside formal employment. Seasonal work patterns were common, particularly in agriculture and construction, where workers moved across regions for temporary contracts (Habib, 1999). Colonial interventions, however, dismantled guilds and imposed exploitative labour systems, replacing collective bargaining with individualized precarious work (Bayly, 2012).

Post-Liberalization and Platformization

With the economic reforms of the 1990s, India experienced a dual shift: the decline of formal employment opportunities and the rise of service-sector jobs. Scholars argue that the current gig economy is an extension of historical informal labour, but technologically mediated through digital platforms (Mehrotra & Parida, 2021).

Platforms act as contemporary equivalents of Shrenis—organizing workers, mediating trust, and connecting them with demand—though without the welfare responsibilities guilds once upheld (Kässi & Lehdonvirta, 2018).

Gig Economy in Contemporary India

The gig economy in India has expanded rapidly due to digital platforms such as Uber, Ola, Swiggy, and Urban Company, which have created millions of jobs but also raised questions of job quality, social security, and fair wages (Aneja & Sridhar, 2019; Fairwork India, 2023). According to Niti Aayog, approximately 7.7 million Indians were engaged in Gig Economy in 2020-21 and this number is expected to rise to 23.5 million by 2029-30. Scholars highlight that gig work offers flexibility and entry-level opportunities but simultaneously reproduces precarity through algorithmic management and lack of worker protections (Rani&Furrer, 2021).

ILO reports (2021) underline the structural vulnerabilities of platform workers, including inconsistent incomes, absence of collective bargaining rights, and exclusion from formal labour benefits. The Fairwork Project in India ranks digital platforms on parameters such as pay, conditions, contracts, management, and representation, showing that most fall short of minimum standards (Fairwork India, 2022).

These jobs attract young workers due to the promise of quick income, flexible hours, and low skill requirements. However, existing studies highlight significant downsides:

- **Income precarity** due to fluctuating demand (Fairwork India, 2023).
- **Algorithmic control**, where workers' autonomy is curtailed by dynamic pricing and customer ratings (Anwar & Graham, 2021).
- **Gender imbalance**, with male dominance in ride-hailing and only limited female participation in food delivery (John, 2022).
- **Lack of social security**, leaving workers vulnerable to economic shocks.

While global research echoes these findings (Woodcock & Graham, 2020), the Indian context reflects deeper continuities with historical informal labour regimes.

3. Research Design

This study adopts a mixed-methods research design, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to explore the quality of work within India's gig economy. By triangulating survey findings with in-depth interview narratives, the study captures both the measurable aspects of gig work and the lived experiences of workers and further investigates if these experiences hold any similarity or difference to that of Gig Economy that existed in Ancient India.

Research Objectives

The primary objectives of this research are:

1. To trace the historical roots of gig-like labour arrangements in India and situate them in relation to contemporary platform-based work.
2. To evaluate the quality of work in the current gig economy using dimensions from the ILO Job Quality Framework and Fairwork India's five principles.
3. To analyse demographic participation trends (with a focus on gender and sectorial distribution) within the Indian gig economy.
4. To highlight continuities and ruptures between ancient informal labour practices and modern platform-mediated gig work.

Research Questions

Guided by the above objectives, the study addresses the following research questions:

1. What historical forms of gig-like work can be identified in India, and how do they compare to the characteristics of today's gig economy?
2. How do gig workers in India evaluate the quality of their jobs in terms of wages, security, working hours, and autonomy?
3. What are the demographic trends in gig work participation, particularly regarding gender and sectorial representation?
4. In what ways do present-day gig platforms perpetuate, modify, or depart from earlier systems of informal labour exchange in India?

Sampling Strategy

The study adopted a two-stage sampling process. First, a pilot survey was conducted with 100 gig workers across platforms engaged in Delivery services and Ride hailing services. A purposive sampling technique was used to ensure representation of both male and female workers, across different age groups and service types.

Second, 15 workers were purposively selected from the survey pool for semi-structured interviews, allowing for deeper exploration of their experiences. Selection emphasized diversity in job satisfaction, tenure on platforms, and gender. The selected platforms included workers from Zomato, Swiggy, Blinkit, Uber, Ola and Rapido. Of 100, surveyed workers, 50 were food delivery workers and 50 were ride hailing drivers.

Data Collection Tools

A Survey Questionnaire of Job quality was Adapted from ILO (2016) and Fairwork (2022), covering wages, hours, job security, and social protections. This was further triangulated with Semi-Structured Interviews with a focus on worker narratives regarding autonomy, customer relations, algorithmic control, and aspirations.

4. Data Analysis

Data was analysed through the use of NVivo 14 for qualitative insights and SPSS (Version 29) for quantitative findings. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, and means) were used to summarize demographic information such as gender, age distribution, and sectorial participation. Cross-tabulation was conducted to compare gender differences across the two sectors. Chi-square tests were employed to examine associations between categorical variables (e.g., gender and sector participation). Additionally, independent samples t-tests were conducted to evaluate differences in earnings, working hours, and job satisfaction levels across male and female workers. The construct, Job quality adapted using scales of ILO and Fairwork was tested using Cronbach's alpha and it was found reliable with value 0.91.

For qualitative analysis, Interview transcripts with 15 gig workers (8 from ride-hailing, 7 from food delivery) were imported into NVivo for thematic coding. Using an inductive coding approach, open coding was first applied to identify recurring themes in workers' narratives. Codes were then clustered into broader categories reflecting key constructs such as flexibility, precarity, customer relations, platform dependency, and gendered experiences.

A thematic analysis was conducted following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step framework. To enhance trustworthiness, the qualitative analysis incorporated triangulation by cross-checking themes with quantitative findings. Member-checking was conducted with three participants to validate interpretations of key themes. NVivo visualizations, such as word clouds and thematic cluster diagrams, were also used to illustrate the salience of recurring patterns in gig workers' experiences.

Finally, a convergent parallel mixed-methods design was adopted to integrate SPSS and NVivo outputs. Quantitative results provided the breadth of statistical trends in gig workers' experiences, while qualitative findings offered depth and contextual nuance. For example, survey results showed that female participation in food delivery services was significantly lower than in ride-hailing; interview data further explained this trend by revealing women's concerns about safety and social stigma associated with delivery work. This integration allowed the study to produce a richer understanding of the continuities and divergences between ancient forms of contingent labour and contemporary gig work in India, situating empirical results within a broader historical and theoretical context.

5. Results and Findings

Of 100 respondents, 92 were males and 8 were females. This indicates limited female participation reflecting cultural barriers and safety concerns in India (Fairwork India, 2023). The Age profile of respondents is as follows.

Table 1: Age profile of respondents

Age in years	Number of respondents
18-24	26
25-34	55
35-44	15
Above 44	4

The majority (55%) belonged to the 25–34 age bracket, confirming that gig work primarily attracts younger workers seeking flexible income options.

Table 2: Income Levels of Respondents

Income levels in Rs.	Number of respondents
Below 10000	24
10000-15000	58
Above 15000	18

Most workers (58%) earned between ₹10,000–15,000, which remains below formal-sector wages in Gujarat.

Table 3: Work hours of respondents

Work hours	Number of respondents
Less than 8 hours	12
8-12 hours	70
Above 12 hours	18

Findings highlight extended working hours, often exceeding labour law thresholds, with implications for fatigue and work–life balance.

Job satisfaction was measured on a five point scale and the results are depicted as follows.

Table 4: Job satisfaction of respondents

Job satisfaction	Number of respondents
Satisfied	20
Neutral	44
Dis-satisfied	36

For qualitative analysis In-depth interviews with 15 respondents were coded and analysed in NVivo 14. Three key themes emerged:

1. Flexibility vs. Work Pressure

Respondents valued the autonomy to log in and out at will, but they also reported algorithmic pressure tied to customer ratings and order acceptance. NVivo coding highlighted recurring phrases such as “freedom but stressful” and “always chasing incentives”.

2. Safety Concerns and Female Participation

Female respondents (n = 8) overwhelmingly cited safety issues as a barrier, particularly for evening shifts. Many emphasized dependence on family support as a reason to continue working. Themes coded included “fear of harassment” and “restricted hours”.

3. Earnings, Aspirations, and Precarious conditions

While most workers expressed dissatisfaction with low earnings, many younger participants saw gig work as temporary income support until securing better jobs. Codes included “stop-gap employment” and “dream of government job”

Integration of Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

Quantitative results confirmed that most workers are male, young, low-earning, and work long hours with modest satisfaction levels. Qualitative themes explained these outcomes: algorithmic controls, safety barriers for women, and aspirations beyond gig work. The combined analysis underscores that gig work provides employment opportunities, but perpetuates insecurity, gender imbalance, and limited upward mobility.

6. Discussion of Results

The findings of this study reaffirm the highly gendered nature of gig work in Gujarat’s platform economy. This trend mirrors broader patterns in India, where women’s participation in the labour force is structurally constrained

by cultural expectations, mobility restrictions, and safety concerns (Fairwork India, 2023). The quantitative results showed that the majority of respondents fell into the 25–34 age group and worked between 8–12 hours daily, reflecting how gig work is attractive to younger individuals seeking flexible income but also exposing them to long working hours without adequate protections. Earnings clustered between ₹10,000–15,000 per month, which is lower than many formal-sector wages in Gujarat, underscoring the precarity of income security in gig work. These results are consistent with earlier studies that have described gig work in India as a low-paying yet accessible alternative to unemployment (Mehrotra, 2021).

With respect to comparison between modern and contemporary Gig work with that of ancient Gig forms of labour, results can be summarised as follows.

Dimension	Ancient Indian Gig-like Work	Modern Gig Work in India
Organization & Support	Shrenis (guilds) provided structure, ethical codes, collective welfare, and training under state respect	Fragmented platform model: operated individually; limited collective bargaining or support—until new laws emerging
Training & Skill Building	Apprenticeship from childhood, including cultural, technical, and trade education; best apprentices incorporated into guilds	Self-up skilling: minimal formal training; most learning is on-the-job or via platform; limited career development
Regulation & Governance	Internal guild laws, state oversight, dispute resolution mechanisms; artisan taxes and ethics regulated under Arthshastra-like frameworks	Unclear regulation: platforms set opaque rules; limited labor law protection; some state-level initiatives (Karnataka, Delhi, Maharashtra) pushing welfare measures
Social/Cultural Value	Craft seen as spiritual , with artists honoring tools and invoking cultural reverence; art was communally celebrated	Gig work is transactional , largely devoid of cultural or spiritual identity; focus is on efficiency and flexibility
Worker Protections	Guilds provided social security, collective charity, support during crises; operated as welfare collectives	Lack of protections: no health, insurance, or retirement benefits; gig workers face financial precarity, long hours, and safety risks; activism growing
Scale & Reach	Geographically local , craft-specific communities; activity centered around temples and localized economies	National, app-enabled; millions engaged across sectors (delivery, rides, freelance); growing exponentially (~7.7M in 2020–21 to projected 23.5M by 2029–30)
Income Stability	Guild membership secured reputation-based work, collective dues, and economic support.	Highly unstable: variable income, costs (fuel, commissions) erode earnings; platform deactivations add risk
Safety & Well-being	Workers more integrated into community with some social safety nets.	Gig workers face physical dangers (accidents, violence, health hazards), especially women; emerging welfare boards aiming to address this

7. Conclusion

Both ancient and modern gig economies reflect flexible, task-based work, frequently chosen or necessitated to survive. They offer autonomy and variety—but also carry risk and instability. However, the scale, technological scaffolding, and regulatory environment of modern gig work mark a radical transformation. Digital platforms bring global reach and efficiency—but also unprecedented legal debates, algorithmic control, and questions about worker rights.

From a policy perspective, the findings suggest that platforms and regulators need to prioritize gender-sensitive policies, fair wage structures, and social protections. For women in particular, investments in safety infrastructure

and supportive policies reflect the need of an hour. At the same time, integrating gig workers into broader labour protection frameworks—such as minimum wage standards, social security benefits, and grievance redressal systems—remains crucial to improving job quality.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no known conflict of interest.

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